

FACTORS INFLUENCE EARLY PREGNANCY TO SECONDARY SCHOOLS STUDENTS IN TANZANIA

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ABSTRACT: This study aimed to investigate factors influence early pregnancy to secondary schools' students in Tanzania. The study was guided by three (3) research questions which cover the aspects such as; factors influence early pregnancy to secondary schools' students, effects of early school pregnancy and measures that should be employed to reduce or eradicate early school pregnancy among secondary school students. All literatures sources concerning factors influence early pregnancy to secondary schools' students, effects of early school pregnancy and measures that should be employed to reduce or eradicate early school pregnancy among secondary school students were reviewed whereby purposeful sampling technique was used for selection of reviewed studies. The study used document review approach. Document analysis guide was used to collect information from 18 reviewed studies. Collected information were analyzed by using narrative synthesis method through textual narrative summaries for describing and identifying patterns and differences between multiple studies from diverse sources in order to address or examine an issue. It was found that home-based factors, students' personal characteristics and economic factors such as family neglect, poor parenting and broken marriages, knowledge on reproductive health services, beliefs and attitudes on sexual health, early sexual practice, cell phone

usage, peer group pressure, poverty level, parental level of education, parental occupation to the large extent influenced early pregnancy. Also, the study revealed that early pregnancy led to school dropout, diseases such as sexual transmitted diseases, anemia, malnutrition and bleeding, poverty, street children, emotional instability, complication during delivery, school attendance, academic performance, emotional behavior, broken marriages and miscarriages, increased family burden and abortion. The study recommends that collaboration of different sectors such as Department of Health, Department of Social Development and Department of Education to work together to address the different levels identified to be influencing early pregnancy among secondary schools' students.

LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

AMREF	African Medical and Research Foundation
DVCAA	Deputy Vice Chancellor Academic Affairs
ETP	Education and Training Policy
HAPA	Health Action Promotion Association
MWECAU	Mwenge Catholic University
NGOs	Non-Government Organizations
NIMR	National Institute for Medical Research
SPSS	Statistical Package for Social Sciences
UNFPA	United Nations Fund for Population Activities
UNICEF	United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund
US	United State
WHO	World Health Organization

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Problem

Early pregnancy occurs in all societies, with considerable variation in magnitude and consequences among different countries and regions. In each case, a variety of complex socioeconomic factors are involved including poverty, communities and family's acceptance of child marriage, culture behaviors, gender inequality, sexual violence, lack of education and information among others.

In 2014, a total of 249,078 babies were born to women aged 15–19 years, for a birth rate of 24.2 per 1,000 women in this age group. This is another historic low for U. S. teens and a drop of 9% from 2013. Birth rates fell 11% for women aged 15–17 years and 7% for women aged 18–19 years. Although reasons for the declines are not clear, more teens may be delaying or reducing sexual activity, and more of the teens who are sexually active may be using birth control than in previous years (Romero *et al*, 2016). Early pregnancy and parenting are significant contributors to high school drop-out rates among teen girls. Thirty percent of teenage girls who drop out of high school cite pregnancy or parenthood as a primary reason. This rate is even higher for Hispanic and African American teens, at 36 and 38 percent, respectively (Patterson, 2008).

In many country contexts, early pregnancy is closely linked to child marriage. 90% of adolescent births among 15–19-year-olds occur within child marriage (UNFPA, 2013). Asian countries such as India, Sri Lanka, Nepal, Maldives, Bhutan and Bangladesh have high proportions of teenage pregnancies, since early marriage is common. Nearly 60% of all girls are married by the age of 18 years and 25% of all girls are married by the age of 15 years in South Asia whereby among of them being students (Mehra and Agrawal, 2003). Child marriage is also associated with limits on education. Both pregnancy and child marriage increase the chances of dropping out of school. Shahidul (2012) also found that, in Bangladesh, girls with lower socioeconomic backgrounds drop out of secondary schools or higher education and this situation inflates dowry in the marriage market of girls.

Gandhi *et al* (2014) contend that pregnancy in very young women is generally considered to be a very high risk event, because teenage schoolgirls are

physically and psychologically immature for reproduction. These young women are not yet ready to be mothers, both psychologically and physically. Marnach, Forrest, and Goldman (2013) further explain that medically, teenage pregnancy maternal and prenatal health is of particular concern among teens that are pregnant or parenting. According to WHO (2013) revealed that student pregnancy has hit hard developed and developing communities, generating a set of problems such as frequent absenteeism and form repetition in schools, dropping out of schools and poor academic performance.

Dropping out of school reduces opportunities for girls'; they miss out on the overall benefits of education that contribute to their physical and emotional growth, including increases in knowledge and life skills, higher self-confidence and better outcomes in life. Also, adolescent mothers are at risk of falling behind with schoolwork due to their double responsibility as students and mothers (Maluli and Bali, 2014). These girls could potentially be offered additional educational guidance to reduce their risk of early pregnancy (Näslund-Hadley and Binstock, 2010; Stoebenau *et al.*, 2015).

Also in 2007, approximately 8,000 girls either dropped out or were expelled from primary and secondary schools due to their pregnancies, while those who had already given birth were barred from returning to school. As a result, pregnant girls and adolescent mothers are restricted to limited employment opportunities given their incomplete education levels (UNICEF, 2010). The topic of adolescent pregnancy is receiving increasing attention in Tanzania from the high rates of female students dropping out from school, prompting NGOs to invest in programs addressing the issue (UNICEF, 2010). In these situations the education sector has a responsibility to protect the rights of girls, to support girls' retention in school and to educate parents and communities about the health risks and rights violations involved in child marriage. Importantly, policy reforms are increasingly being implemented to prevent child marriage and to respond to early pregnancy. Challenges however remain, due to entrenched unequal gender norms and the lack of enactment of such policy instruments.

In Tanzania, for about more than eight years now different actors including the PAMOJA TUNAWEZA Alliance comprised of five organizations namely, African Medical and Research Foundation (AMREF) Health Africa, Restless Development, Health Action Promotion Association (HAPA), National Institute for Medical Research (NIMR) Mwanza Centre and Medicos Del Mundo have been advocating for government to operationalize the National Education and Training Policy (ETP) which allows girls to return school after they have given birth and also recommending that, sexual and reproductive education be given to young girls and young mothers. The findings of the report based on the survey conducted in Kilindi, Mkalama, Iringa Rural and Same indicated that 55,000 girls were expelled from school between 2003 and 2012 out of which a huge number was students from secondary school and one of the reasons is hardness of life from their home or at school. Actors in the national and international arena advocating for the educational rights of an estimated 8,000 expelled pregnant school girls condemn discriminatory education policies (Niskanen, 2012).

Makundi (2010) commented that majority of teenagers are exposed to high risk of early pregnancies, sexually transmitted diseases and HIV due to the fact that sexual activity among youth is a common habit in Mtwara Municipality. Another by Magareth (2010) whose major discoveries were that the educational status and knowledge of reproductive health of these teenagers was low and there were already dropouts from school. Nyakubega (2010) discovered that early childbearing, particularly among teenagers (those under 20 years of age) had negative demographic, socio-economic and socio-cultural consequences.

Another survey conducted by Restless Development in 2014, showed that 90% of 101 girls who dropped out from school were barred refused re-entry and this concurred with UNDF (2015), survey on “Teenage pregnancies and comprehensive sexual education” provision among young people in schools and out of schools. The survey findings revealed that 23 percent of young women aged 15 to 19 already begun children bearing while 15% of them started having sex at the age of 15 and one of the reasons is poverty whereby most of parents allowed their girls get married.

On 2017, the President of Tanzania, Hon. John Pombe Magufuli came under intense criticisms following his remarks that students who give birth should not be allowed to return to school. According to law in Tanzania which was passed in 2002 allows for the expulsion of pregnant school girls. This law says the girls can be expelled and excluded from school for offences against morality and wedlock.

The president made these remarks on June 22, 2017, while addressing the Bagamoyo District residents in his 3-day tour to the Coast Region, Tanzania. The leader said that pregnant girls should not be allowed to go back to school after they deliver, arguing they would not be able to concentrate. Also, he warned school girls at a rally on June 19th, 2017 that after getting pregnant, you are done. According to him, they are no longer girls but parents and should not be allowed to enjoy the free education benefits meant for children. Moreover, he argued that if such girls were to be allowed back to school, then they would encourage other girls to engage in premarital sex. He, however, suggested other areas where girls in this category can fit into after delivery; they can join Vocational Education Training Authority Centers or they can learn sewing but they cannot be allowed to go back to school.

Therefore, early pregnancy is still the serious problem in Tanzania numerous investigations have been carried out to demonstrate the issue of early pregnancy among secondary school students and the results are published in various newspaper, magazines, journals and on various television stations. For instance, The Guardian newspaper (July 11th, 2010) reported a young lady (under 18) with her four-month baby. According to this newspaper the baby was born when the mother was in form two, and this was her end of studies. Nevertheless, most secondary school students do not plan to get pregnancy but many do get it simply because of life hardships in the school or at home. Therefore, this study investigated the factors influencing early pregnancy to secondary school students in Tanzania.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Early pregnancy for school girls has been a problem of girl's education in the country. When, a girl gets pregnant while studying she drops out of school. Although the elimination of school fees, parents are often unable to meet other school costs such as transport, school uniforms and other expenses. This poses a big challenge to

student to find another way so as to meet these demands. Actors in the national and international arena advocating for the educational rights of an estimated 8,000 expelled pregnant school girls condemn discriminatory education policies (Niskanen, 2012). It has been recognized that pregnancy and childbirth have a significant impact on educational outcomes of teen parents. Furthermore, in the case of Africa, the success of the measures that has been taken by the government in reducing the problem of early pregnancy is still questionable. Though, for the government to take sound measures to solve the problem successfully it needs to understand the possible cause of early pregnancy that requires accurate information of the problem.

Studies have been undertaken to explore the factors responsible for the increase of the pregnancies in Tanzania. Makundi (2010) commented that the increase is due to early sexual activities among the youths in the region which is taken as a common habit. Magareth (2010) major discoveries were that the educational status and knowledge of reproductive health of these teenagers was low and there were already dropouts from school. Nyakubega (2010) discovered that early childbearing, particularly among teenagers (those under 20 years of age) had negative demographic, socio-economic and socio-cultural consequences. Irrespective of these studies, still the findings on the causes of early pregnancy are not the same since they differ from one another. Moreover, having no study that has been undertaken to assess the factors responsible for early pregnancies in Africanity, it demands for further study to investigate the reasons of the problem necessary for providing desirable information to take appropriate and operational measures to solve it. Thus, the aim of this study was to assess the factors influencing early pregnancy to secondary schools' students in Tanzania.

1.3 Research Objectives

1.3.1 General Objective

The main objective of the study was to investigate factors influence early pregnancy to secondary schools' students in Tanzania.

1.3.2 Specific Objectives

The following are the specific objectives within which this study was conducted.

- i. To examine the factors causing early pregnancy to secondary schools' students in Tanzania.
- ii. To investigate the effects of early school pregnancy to the secondary schools' students in Tanzania.
- iii. To discover the measures that should be employed to reduce or eradicate early school pregnancy among secondary school students in Tanzania.

1.4 Research Questions

This study was guided by the following research questions; -

1. What are the factors causing early pregnancy to secondary schools' students in Tanzania?
2. To what extent do the early school pregnancy affect secondary schools' students in Tanzania?
3. What are the measures that should be employed to reduce or eradicate early school pregnancy among secondary school students in Tanzania?

1.5 Significance of the Study

The findings of this study would add to the body of knowledge about factors influence early pregnancy to secondary schools' students in Tanzania. This study also would shed light to policy makers and educators to frame strategies that guide student girl not to get pregnancy. Furthermore, the study would set on the basis for further study about factors influence early pregnancy to secondary schools' students. Finally, the study would help community members including parents to understand and provide the educational and moral support needed by their children to boost their progressive towards avoiding pregnancies at early age.

1.6 Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study was confirmed to university library research due to the presence of pandemic disease COVID-19; therefore, the study used only secondary data from library sources as the way to avoid spread of COVID-19 by collecting primary data

in groups of respondents. The study focuses in discovering information on factors influence early pregnancy to secondary schools' students in Tanzania. It did not address the primary level because majority of them are under age of conceiving. The study involved secondary schools due to the expectancy of collecting reliable information within a time limit allocated because the researcher is familiar with the geographical area of Tanzania. The study involved all literatures sources concerning factors influence early pregnancy to secondary schools' students, effects of early school pregnancy and measures that should be employed to reduce or eradicate early school pregnancy among secondary school students.

1.7 Theoretical Framework

1.7.1 Systems Approach Theory

The founder of system approach theory is Bertalanffy (1968). The theory explains that a system is a set of interrelated elements where each element has an effect on the functioning of the whole and each is affected by at least one other element in the system. It explains the system into three elements of input, output and process. The input is something entered into the system for processing and output is the results of input factor (Irby, 2013). For this case, early pregnancy rates are one such phenomenon that can be explained as a product of functional elements within the education system. Early pregnancy in secondary schools can be influenced with many factors such as home-based factors, culture of the community, and economic status of the family and student personal characteristics as the inputs to the students' early pregnancy in secondary school as the output.

Strength of the Theory

The strength of system theory in guiding this study is that early pregnancy is an output of the school's educational activities and a function of the household factors such as family type, household size, household income and parental level of education which are associated with the school system. These elements do not operate in isolation but are interrelated making school early pregnancy a process.

Weakness of the Theory

The systems theory does not consider the organization context because it focuses only on the input, process and outputs. Measuring the means, or process of school

system can be very difficult when compared to measuring specific end goals. The theory has been criticized that it focuses on the means to achieve goals and objectives rather than school system effectiveness itself in controlling early pregnancy in secondary schools' students. For example, if there is no positive interaction between teachers, parents and students then the influence on early pregnancy in secondary schools' students will be very higher.

Application and Justifications of the Theory to the Study

The applicability of the theory in this study is in the fact that systems theory indicates how inputs, process and outputs interact to yield desirable results. The school is a system which is often affected by other systems in the environment for example; household background of students, students' personal characteristics and economic factors determine completion of early pregnancy in secondary schools. Therefore, using this theory the study seeks to investigate the factors leading to early pregnancy to secondary schools' students in Tanzania.

1.8 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework indicates clearly the organization of the variables in the study as follows:

Figure 1.1: Conceptual Framework
Source: Researcher Own Construction (2026)

Figure 1.1 indicates the relationship of the variables in the study. The independent variable of the study is the factors leading to early pregnancy in secondary schools students. These independent factors are home based factors, students' personal characteristics and economic factors. The intervening variable or process are those extra factors which can influence early pregnancy in secondary schools. Such factors are parental-child communication and sexual activity. The dependent variable of the study is the early pregnancy in secondary schools in Africa secondary schools.

1.9 Operational Definitions of Key Terms

Education: Is the process of facilitating learning, or the acquisition of knowledge, skills, values, beliefs, and habits.

Pregnancy: A state of having a developing embryo in the body after success conception. In this study, it refers to as a process whereby a female carries a live offspring from the time of conception to childbirth.

Secondary schools: Schools that offer programs that are four years long including practical skills.

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

This chapter presents a review of related literature; it focuses on what other researchers have found out about factors influence early pregnancy to secondary schools' students. These studies helped the researcher to identify the knowledge gap and justify the need to carry out research in Tanzania. The chapter is organized under the following sub sections: review of different related theories and review of empirical studies and knowledge gap.

2.2 Theoretical Review

2.2.1 Social Learning Theory

The theory was proposed by Albert Bandura (1977). It explains how people observe and learn different behaviors and characteristics from other people in the society.

This theory also explained about social interaction and its influence of some groups of people to other people in the society. This theory explains that one group of people can influence other people to engage in good or bad behavior through learning and observing the behavior and actions of that group. This theory shows the learning which occurs to social groups and these groups may include the family, peers' groups and larger community. Children or youth learn and observe different behavior and actions done by these kinds of groups in their society and cause them to engage in that kind of actions like, sexual relationship, drug abuse and crime actions ((Bandura, 1977).

Strengths of the theory

The Social learning theory is accurately and easy to understand, explains a large number of behaviors also it accurately picture explaining how behavior is learned. Furthermore, the theory offers a way to integrate social and cognitive theories. Since the theory is based upon observable behaviors, so it is easier to quantify and collect data and information when conducting research.

Weaknesses of the Theory

The theory is too heavy of an emphasis on what happens instead of what the observer does with what happens, it does not take into account physical and mental changes, it doesn't explain all behavior and behavioral differences on other hand the theory does not take in account that what one person views as punishment, another person may view as a reward. Bandura (1977) and his colleagues developed conceptions of modeling and mechanisms of internalization but ignored reinforcement and punishment, even though they are the central concepts of the learning theory.

Application of the Theory to the Study

Social Learning Theory can be effectively used to understand the occurrence and reoccurrence of early pregnancy. The concepts of differential association, definitions, imitation and differential reinforcement can be used to explore the different sides of early pregnancy. Social Learning theory will be helpful in explaining the onset of early pregnancy and further conformation to this behavior code. This study used

social learning theory to understand factors enhancing early pregnancy to secondary school students and how to reduce unexpected behavior.

2.3 Review of Empirical Studies

This section reviews the empirically related literature that supported the need of the current study conducted on factors influence early pregnancy to secondary schools' students. The researcher reviewed several studies based on themes drawn from the research questions as follows:

(Achema, Emmanuel, & Ao, 2015) conducted the study on Factors responsible for teenage pregnancy and its implication on adolescent health and education: Perception of secondary school students in Nigeria. A descriptive survey design was adopted, and 300 students were randomly selected from two secondary schools to complete a self-administered questionnaire. Findings reveal that most (46.7%) students admitted that lack of parenting care was responsible for teenage pregnancy. Furthermore, lack of self-control (36.7%) and lack of sex education (13.3%) were identified as responsible factors for teenage pregnancy to occur. Majority of the students (60%) admitted that polygamous family system acted as contributory parenting factor for teenage pregnancy. On their health and educational implication, a greater percentage (60%) among the respondents stated that teenage pregnancy could lead to school dropout, and some (20%) among the respondents admitted that it could lead to abortion, while 16.7% believe that it could lead to sexually transmitted infections. On the aftermath implication during pregnancy and delivery, most of the respondents (60.7%) acknowledged that it could lead to malnutrition, anaemia and bleeding.

(Gyan, 2013) did a study on effects of teenage pregnancy on the educational attainment of the girl-child at Chorkor, a Suburb of Accra. Purposive and snowball sampling procedures were used in selecting respondents for the study. A total sample size of fifty-five (55) respondents was used for the study. Questionnaire, in-depth interview, focus group discussions and observation were used to collect data for the study. With respect to factors that lead to teenage pregnancy, it was evident that poor parenting, poverty and peer influence are the major causes of teenage pregnancy. The study also revealed that most of the teenage mothers drop out of school.

Emmanuel and Abimbola (2012). carried out a study about factors associated with teenage pregnancy and fertility in Nigeria. The study used the 2008 Nigerian Demographic and Health Survey Data. A subset of women aged 15-19 was extracted from the women data. The study was set to find out the variables that predict the odds of teenagers being currently pregnant. The results showed that, apart from the age of teenager, marital status is another strong predictor of the likelihood of being currently pregnant/having a child in the 5 years preceding the survey. The study, further, suggests that poverty may be a contributing factor to teenage pregnancy and teenage child bearing; for only teenagers from the richest quintile household are significantly less to be currently pregnant/have a child in five years before the survey (Emmanuel and Abimbola, 2012). Therefore, the study suggested that ensuring that teenagers remain in school to secondary level of education may be a way out of reducing the negative outcomes of teenage pregnancy and child bearing.

(Alhassan, 2015) examined the socio-economic causes of early pregnancy, psychological causes as well as its implications in Talensi District of the Upper East Region of Ghana. Non-pregnant and pregnant teenage girls were selected using probability and non-probability samplings techniques. Data was collected through semi-structured interview schedules and structured questionnaires and analyses were done with the help of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences involving frequency tables, percentages as well as charts. The results showed that cell phone usage by teenagers, inadequate contraceptives; peer group influence, family neglect and poverty had a negative and detrimental effect on teenagers' academic career, increased family burden and sexual transmitted diseases. The study also revealed that sex and sexuality learning programmes should be introduced in JHS, ban the open dances at funeral centers and provide contraceptives at vantage points, establishment of youth centers and finally, establishment of parent information sessions in various communities of the district. These would go a long way to reduce the incidence of early pregnancy.

Malisa (2015) attempted to assess the factors contributing to teenage pregnancy in Tunduru District Council. Cross sectional research design was used to show and also help in investigating associations between risk factors and the outcome of interest.

Purposive sampling technique was used because it enabled the researcher to include only the respondents that were needed for the study. The target population consisted of 183 respondents who satisfied the inclusion criteria. Primary data were collected from the respondents using self-administered questionnaires via the reproductive health service providers. Both qualitative and quantitative methods of data analysis were used to analyze data in order to minimize the weakness of one another and thereafter SPSS program version 20 was used to code them. The results revealed that poverty, peer pressure, level of education, poor knowledge on the use of family planning contraceptives, reproductive health, little access of family planning methods, early marriages and low access to family services contributed much to the problem. Pregnancy prevention strategies were recommended based on the results. The strategies focused on improving female literacy rate, establishment of adolescent friendly clinics, revision of the current marriage law, encourage community-based programmes for sensitization purposes, establishment of gender help desk specifically for youths in order to help them when in need and many others.

(Mathewos & Mekuria, 2017) assessed the prevalence of teenage pregnancy and its associated factors among school adolescents of Arba Minch Town, Southern Ethiopia. Institution-based, cross-sectional study was conducted from 20-30 March 2014. Systematic sampling technique was used to select a total of 578 students from four schools of the town. Data were collected by trained data collectors using a pre-tested, self-administered structured questionnaire. Analysis was made using SPSS version 20.0 statistical packages. Multivariate logistic regression was used to identify the predictors of teenage pregnancy. The prevalence of teenage pregnancy among school adolescents of Arba Minch Town was 7.7%. Being grade 11 student (AOR=4.6; 95% CI:1.4,9.3), grade 12 students (AOR=5.8; 95% CI:1.3,14.4), not knowing the exact time to take emergency contraceptives (AOR=3.3; 95%CI:1.4,7.4), substance use (AOR=3.1; 95%CI:1.1,8.8), living with either of biological parents (AOR=3.3; 95%CI:1.1,8.7) and poor parent-daughter interaction (AOR=3.1; 95%CI:1.1,8.7) were found to be significant predictors of teenage pregnancy.

Thobejane (2015) investigated the causes and effects of teenage pregnancy in Matjitjileng Village, a sub-rural area situated in the Mogalakwena Municipality in Waterberg District of Limpopo Province, South Africa. The study found that most of the teenagers fell pregnant at the age of 16 and 19 years. Almost all of them fall pregnant because of lack of parental guidance and role models in the village. Most of them were influenced by their peers who fell pregnant at an early age and were ignorant about contraceptives. The study suggested radical programs that are aimed at the reduction of teenage pregnancy and the holding of workshops that encourage abstinence and preventative measures against this scourge.

Kate (2012) investigated the educators' perceptions of the effects of teenage pregnancy on the behaviour of secondary school learners in Mankweng area, Limpopo province. The study sought to establish whether teenage pregnancy has an effect on school attendance, school performance and emotional behaviour of pregnant learners as perceived by educators. Fourteen educators from seven secondary schools in Mankweng area were purposively sampled for the study. Data was collected using in-depth interviews to allow the researcher a platform to ask open-response questions and to explore the educators' perspectives about the effects of teenage pregnancy. The data was analysed thematically by carefully identifying and expanding significant themes that emerged from the informants' perceptions about the effects of teenage pregnancy. The study revealed that teenage pregnancy has a negative or detrimental effect on the school attendance, academic performance, emotional behaviour and relationships between pregnant teenagers, their peers and educators. The study recommends that sex education should be taken seriously in secondary schools; educators should liaise with health professionals in the community; pregnant learners to be supported and not humiliated or stigmatized by school stakeholders; educators to encourage teenagers to use preventative and protective measures and to encourage learners to delay engaging in sexual relationships.

2.4 Demonstration of Knowledge Gap

Previously, a lot of researches published and unpublished, had been done on this topic focusing on socio-economic factors influencing adolescents' and early

pregnancies at Global, Africa and Tanzania, but they were not detail and not specific to Tanzania. This study differs from previous study under aspects of socio-economic factors influencing early pregnancies, research methods, population sample, and area of the study research type and study time. It is the aim of this study, therefore to analyze in depth factors which are responsible for early pregnancy to secondary schools' students in Tanzania.

RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This chapter describes research design and methodology that were hired in data collection and analysis to address the problem in the study. Specifically, the chapter focused on the research design, targeted population, description of the sample and sampling procedures, description of data collection instruments, description of data collection procedures, description of data analysis procedures and ethical consideration in research.

3.2 Research Design

This study used document review approach to systematically investigate factors influence early pregnancy to secondary schools' students in Tanzania. The study used document review approach because it enabled the researcher to collect data from different best sources for information concerning factors influence early pregnancy to secondary schools' students. Document review approach was appropriate in this study as it granted the researcher the opportunity to visit different sites and obtain information from different literature sources pertaining to the research questions.

3.3 Target Population

The study target population are all literatures sources concerning factors influence early pregnancy to secondary schools' students. The total population comprised the resources such as journals, dissertations, and internet sources. The study targeted these sources because they guaranteed rich information on factors influence early pregnancy to secondary schools' students.

3.4 Description of the Sample and Sampling Procedures

3.4.1 Sample

Sample is the sub set of a population that is used to represent the entire group accurately as a whole (Kothari, 2004). The sample size of the study was 18 literature pertaining factors influence early pregnancy to secondary schools' students, effects of early school pregnancy and measures that should be employed to reduce or eradicate early school pregnancy among secondary school students from 2010 up to 2020. This period was selected in order to have the nearest ten year follow up period.

3.4.2 Sampling Procedure

The study used non-probability sampling technique where purposeful sampling method was employed to select documents or literature concerning factors influence early pregnancy to secondary schools' students, effects of early school pregnancy and measures that should be employed to reduce or eradicate early school pregnancy among secondary school students from 2010 up to 2020. The researcher used purposeful sampling method because it enabled researchers to squeeze a lot of information out of the data that they have collected. This allowed researchers to describe the major impact their findings have on the population.

3.5 Description of Data Collection Instruments

The researcher gathered all research papers through document analysis guide. All available information on factors influences early pregnancy to secondary schools' students, effects of early school pregnancy and measures that should be employed to reduce or eradicate early school pregnancy among secondary school students from 2010 up to 2020 was checked from different literatures reviewed with modification to meet the study questions.

3.6 Description of Data Collection Procedures

3.6.1 Search Strategy

A systematic review of English literature was performed on December 2019 to identify primary research articles focusing on factors influence early pregnancy to secondary schools' students, effects of early school pregnancy and measures that

should be employed to reduce or eradicate early school pregnancy among secondary school students. The articles were published from 2010 to 2020. This time frame was chosen in order to limit the study to contemporary studies, as the factors influence early pregnancy to secondary schools' students, effects of early school pregnancy and measures that should be employed to reduce or eradicate early school pregnancy among secondary school students in older studies may no longer be relevant. An electronic search was conducted using online databases. This review was developed and reported according to the research questions.

Data collection form was developed by the researcher. On conducting the screening, the researcher used the data extraction tool to independently extract the following information from each article: (1) sample size; (2) country where the study was conducted in; (3) study design (quantitative, qualitative and mixed); (4) data collection procedures (self-administered structured questionnaire, interview guide/schedules and focus group); (5) sampling strategy; (6) factors influence early pregnancy to secondary schools students, effects of early school pregnancy and measures that should be employed to reduce or eradicate early school pregnancy among secondary school students.

3.6.2 Eligibility Criteria

Eligibility for inclusion in the review was primary, original research studies published in English, reporting on factors influence early pregnancy to secondary schools' students, effects of early school pregnancy and measures that should be employed to reduce or eradicate early school pregnancy among secondary school students in Tanzania. Included studies used quantitative, qualitative or mixed methods approaches. Excluded studies were those not talking about factors influence early pregnancy to secondary schools' students, effects of early school pregnancy and measures that should be employed to reduce or eradicate early school pregnancy among secondary school students. Also excluded were conference abstracts, editorials, commentaries and study protocols.

3.6.3 Study Selection

Abstracts were screened according to the aforementioned criteria, and full texts were retrieved for eligible studies. At full-text review, in addition to the aforementioned

criteria, studies were excluded if they did not focus on factors influence early pregnancy to secondary schools' students, effects of early school pregnancy and measures that should be employed to reduce or eradicate early school pregnancy among secondary school students. The researcher independently screened the titles and abstracts of articles retrieved from the literature search, and the full texts of potentially eligible articles were obtained and further assessed for final inclusion.

3.7 Description of Data Analysis Procedure

The method of synthesis chosen for this review was the narrative synthesis method using textual narrative summaries to analyze the data. This method is useful for describing and identifying patterns and differences between multiple studies from diverse sources in order to address or examine an issue. Narrative synthesis allows primary data to be summarized and described in a clear and structured manner allowing gaps in research to be found more easily and future research implications to be provided. In a narrative synthesis, identified factors are combined into more homogenous groups. The researcher grouped the multiple items found in selected studies into three themes (factors influence early pregnancy, effects and measures to reduce or eradicate early school pregnancy). Similar factors influence early pregnancy, effects of early school pregnancy and measures to reduce or eradicate early school pregnancy were grouped into the same theme, making it easier to identify patterns between studies.

3.8 Ethical Consideration

The researcher observed research regulations and being responsible for all data collected and the findings distributed. All cited works were duly acknowledged.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

4.1 Introduction

The study aimed to investigate factors influence early pregnancy to secondary schools' students in Tanzania. The study was guided by three questions which are; factors influence early pregnancy to secondary schools' students, effects of early

school pregnancy and measures that should be employed to reduce or eradicate early school pregnancy among secondary school students. This was possible where literatures pertaining factors influence early pregnancy to secondary schools' students were reviewed. The obtained information was analyzed by using narrative synthesis method through textual narrative summaries for describing and identifying patterns and differences between multiple studies from diverse sources in order to address or examine an issue.

4.2 Research Findings

4.2.1 Factors Influencing Early Pregnancy to Secondary Schools Students

In this question the researcher sought to examine factors causing early pregnancy to secondary schools' students in Tanzania. To generate information on this question, narrative synthesis method using textual narrative summaries was used to get information from reviewed literatures. The study found that most (46.7%) students admitted that lack of parenting care was responsible for teenage pregnancy, lack of self-control (36.7%), lack of sex education (13.3%) and majority of the students (60%) admitted that polygamous family system acted as contributory parenting factor for teenage pregnancy (Achema, Emmanuel, & Ao, 2015). It was evident that poor parenting, poverty and peer influence are the major causes of teenage pregnancy (Gyan, 2013; Qolesa, 2017). In one study it was cited that poverty may be a contributing factor to teenage pregnancy and teenage child bearing; for only teenagers from the richest quintile household are significantly less to be currently pregnant/have a child (Emmanuel and Abimbola, 2012).

In one study by Alhassan (2015) on socio-economic causes of early pregnancy, psychological causes in Ghana found that cell phone usage by teenagers, inadequate contraceptives; peer group influence, family neglect and poverty had a negative and detrimental effect on teenagers' academic career. These findings correlate with those findings of Malimbwi (2018) who revealed that there are several factors leading to adolescents' pregnancies which include parents/guardian economic status, physio local needs, globalization, peer pressure, type of girls' family, non-use of contraceptives and sexual abuse/violence. Also, the findings revealed that poverty, lack of sex education, loose of love, care and appreciation also seem to be factors for

adolescents' pregnancies. Moreover, Kimemia (2015) who investigated the influence of cultural factors, economic factors, peer group pressure and social media on teenage pregnancies among public secondary school students revealed that most parent /parents taking their children to the school are into business and electronic media influences teenagers to have sex at an early age and those students are pressurized to have sex by their friends.

Also, a study from Sub-Saharan Africa by Gunawardena, Fantaye, & Yaya (2019) it was found that the most obvious predictors included sexual coercion and pressure from male partners, low or incorrect use of contraceptives, and poor parenting or low parental communication and support. According to Malisa (2015) on the other hand, poverty, peer pressure, level of education, poor knowledge on the use of family planning contraceptives, reproductive health, little access of family planning methods, early marriages and low access to family services contributed much to the problem of early pregnancy. The prevalence of teenage pregnancy among school adolescents was not knowing the exact time to take emergency contraceptives (AOR=3.3; 95% CI:1.4,7.4), substance use (AOR=3.1; 95% CI:1.1,8.8), living with either of biological parents (AOR=3.3; 95% CI:1.1,8.7) and poor parent-daughter interaction (AOR=3.1; 95% CI:1.1,8.7) were found to be significant predictors of teenage pregnancy (Mathewos & Mekuria, 2017).

Additionally, Thobejane (2015) found that most of the teenagers fell pregnant at the age of 16 and 19 years. Almost all of them fall pregnant because of lack of parental guidance and role models in the village. Also, most of them were influenced by their peers who fell pregnant at an early age and were ignorant about contraceptives. These findings concur with Manzi *et al*, (2018) who disclosed that dad peer groups, enticement with gifts and poverty are the most common causes of teenage pregnancy. Lack of knowledge by the girls, peer pressure and the influence of mass media, poverty caused most of the girls to engage in sex (Maritim, Ngeno, & Sang, 2017). In another scenario, other students get pregnant expecting their boyfriends to marry them, or because they did not think they could become pregnant, or failed to use contraception correctly (Salasiah, Al-Adib, and Rosmawati, 2012). With respect to influencing factor on Pregnancy among Secondary School Students, it was evident

that parenting style, material gain, sexual desire, peer influence, media and awareness were the major influencing factors on student pregnancy (Ramadhani, 2018; Mushwana *et al.*, 2015).

Therefore, in this study it was confident to say factors causing early pregnancy to secondary schools students includes lack/poor parenting care, lack of self-control, lack of sex education polygamous family system, poverty, bad peer group, cell phone usage by teenagers, inadequate and non-use of contraceptives, parents/guardian economic status, physiological needs, globalization, type of girls' family, sexual abuse/violence, low parental communication and support, poor knowledge on the use of family planning contraceptives, reproductive health, little access of family planning methods, early marriages and low access to family services, enticement with gifts and other students get pregnant expecting their boyfriends to marry them.

4.2.2 Effects of Early School Pregnancy to Secondary Schools Students

The study intended to investigate the effects of early school pregnancy to the secondary schools' students. To generate information on this question, narrative synthesis method using textual narrative summaries was used to get information from reviewed literatures on effects/impacts of early school pregnancy to the secondary schools' students. In one study it was discovered that early school pregnancy increase school dropout rate, street children; poverty and diseases (Ramadhani, 2018). In one study by Stephen *et al* (2017) ascertained that consequences of teenage pregnancy include emotional instability, complication during delivery and reproductive health problems. Kate (2012) did a study on educators' perceptions of the effects of teenage pregnancy on the behaviour of secondary school learners in Mankweng area, Limpopo province and found that teenage pregnancy has a negative or detrimental effect on the school attendance, academic performance, emotional behaviour and relationships between pregnant teenagers, their peers and educators.

In another study it was showed that 33 (0.4%) out of 7609 (100%) became pregnant, 16 (48.5%) of the pregnant girls came back to school while 17 (51.5%) dropped out completely in Kericho County, Kenya (Maritim, Ngeno, & Sang, 2017). In one study conducted in Uganda on factors associated with teenage pregnancy and its effects

and discovered that school dropout, broken marriages and miscarriages as the major effects (Manzi *et al*, 2018). According to Alhassan (2015) ascertained that early pregnancy had a negative and detrimental effect on teenagers' academic career, increased family burden and sexual transmitted diseases. Gyan (2013) posits that most of the teenage mothers drop out of school.

According to law in Tanzania which was passed in 2002 said that the girls can be expelled and excluded from school for offences against morality and wedlock and the president of Tanzania made the remarks on 2017 that pregnant girls should not be allowed to go back to school after they deliver, arguing they would not be able to concentrate because they are no longer girls but parents and should not be allowed to enjoy the free education benefits meant for children. Moreover, he argued that if such girls were to be allowed back to school, then they would encourage other girls to engage in premarital sex. On their health and educational implication, a greater percentage (60%) among the respondents stated that teenage pregnancy could lead to school dropout, and some (20%) among the respondents admitted that it could lead to abortion, while 16.7% believe that it could lead to sexually transmitted infections. On the aftermath implication during pregnancy and delivery, most of the respondents (60.7%) acknowledged that it could lead to malnutrition, anaemia and bleeding (Achema, Emmanuel, & Ao, 2015).

Therefore, on the effects of student pregnancy among secondary school's student revealed that, the early school pregnancy led to school dropout, diseases such as sexual transmitted diseases, anemia, malnutrition and bleeding, poverty, street children, emotional instability, complication during delivery, school attendance, academic performance, emotional behavior, broken marriages and miscarriages, increased family burden and abortion.

4.2.3 Measures that should be employed to reduce or eradicate Early School Pregnancy among Secondary School Students

The study anticipated to explore measures that should be employed to reduce or eradicate early school pregnancy among secondary school students. To generate information on this question, narrative synthesis method using textual narrative

summaries was used to get information from reviewed literatures. Alhassan (2015) elects that sex and sexuality learning programs should be introduced, ban the open dances at funeral centers and provide contraceptives at vantage points, establishment of youth centers and finally, establishment of parent information sessions in various communities of the district. In one study conducted by Malimbwi (2018) asserted that government in collaboration with department of secondary education should provide hostels, sex education and parents should full engage in preventing adolescents pregnancies. Efforts on educating people regarding teenage pregnancy should be focused on areas experiencing high levels of poverty, government with the help of NGOs should also ensure that parents are well educated on the how and when to talk about sex with their children and parental communication on peer group pressure could reduce chances of teenage pregnancy (Kimemia, 2015).

Kate (2012) suggested that sex education should be taken seriously in secondary schools; educators should liaise with health professionals in the community; pregnant learners to be supported and not humiliated or stigmatized by school stakeholders; educators to encourage teenagers to use preventative and protective measures and to encourage learners to delay engaging in sexual relationships. Massive public campaign and availability of family planning services (Stephen *et al.*, 2017). Ensuring that teenagers remain in school to secondary level of education may be a way out of reducing the negative outcomes of teenage pregnancy and child bearing (Emmanuel and Abimbola, 2012).

Therefore, the study discovered that; measures that should be employed to reduce or eradicate early school pregnancy among secondary school students includes sex and sexuality learning programmes should be introduced, ban the open dances at funeral centers and provide contraceptives at vantage points, establishment of youth centers and finally, establishment of parent information sessions in various communities of the district, efforts on educating people regarding teenage pregnancy should be focused on areas experiencing high levels of poverty, government with the help of NGOs should also ensure that parents are well educated on the how and when to talk about sex with their children and parental communication on peer group pressure, pregnant learners to be supported and not humiliated or stigmatized by school

stakeholders; educators to encourage teenagers to use preventative and protective measures and to encourage learners to delay engaging in sexual relationships, building of hostels, punishment for those who impregnate students and to the large extent, collaboration between parents and teachers should be also considered so as to monitor and control the behavior of students. All these would go a long way to reduce the incidence of early pregnancy in secondary schools.

4.3 Discussion of Findings

4.3.1 Similarities of the Studies

Both studies based on explaining factors responsible for teenage pregnancy and its implication. Most of the studies used quantitative research design method and questionnaires and interview schedules as the tools of data collection and the data were analyzed in term of frequency and percentage. Both studies their findings revealed that factors causing early pregnancy to secondary schools students includes lack/poor parenting care, lack of self-control, lack of sex education polygamous family system, poverty, bad peer group, cell phone usage by teenagers, inadequate and non-use of contraceptives, parents/guardian economic status, physiological needs, globalization, type of girls' family, sexual abuse/violence, low parental communication and support, poor knowledge on the use of family planning contraceptives, reproductive health, little access of family planning methods, early marriages and low access to family services, enticement with gifts and other students get pregnant expecting their boyfriends to marry them.

Also, it was revealed that early school pregnancy lead to school dropout, diseases such as sexual transmitted diseases, anemia, malnutrition and bleeding, poverty, street children, emotional instability, complication during delivery, school attendance, academic performance, emotional behavior, broken marriages and miscarriages, increased family burden and abortion and measures that should be employed to reduce or eradicate early school pregnancy among secondary school students includes sex and sexuality learning programmes, establishment of parent information sessions in various communities of the district, efforts on educating people regarding teenage pregnancy should be focused on areas experiencing high levels of poverty, government with the help of NGOs should also ensure that parents

are well educated on the how and when to talk about sex with their children and parental communication on peer group pressure, pregnant learners to be supported and not humiliated or stigmatized by school stakeholders; educators to encourage teenagers to use preventative and protective measures and to encourage learners to delay engaging in sexual relationships, building of hostels, punishment for those who impregnate students and to the large extent, collaboration between parents and teachers should be also considered so as to monitor and control the behavior of students. All these would go a long way to reduce the incidence of early pregnancy in secondary schools.

4.3.2 Contradiction of the Studies

The studies investigated factors associated with teenage pregnancy or socio-economic causes of early pregnancy, psychological causes as well as its implications but they based only at Global, Africa, but they were not detail and not specific to Tanzania.

4.3.3 Knowledge Gap

This study analyzes in depth factors which are responsible for early pregnancy to secondary schools' students in Tanzania under the aspects of socio-economic factors influencing early pregnancies, research methods, population sample, and area of the study research type and study time. The presence of those factors influences girls' students to be in high risk of being pregnant at the early age especially when they in schools.

4.3.4 Implication of the Findings

The findings of the studies revealed that lack/poor parenting care, lack of self-control, lack of sex education polygamous family system, poverty, bad peer group, cell phone usage by teenagers, inadequate and non-use of contraceptives, parents/guardian economic status, physiological needs, globalization, type of girls' family, sexual abuse/violence, low parental communication and support, poor knowledge on the use of family planning contraceptives, reproductive health, little access of family planning methods, early marriages and low access to family

services, enticement with gifts are factors responsible for early pregnancy at secondary schools. Nevertheless, early school pregnancy led to school dropout, diseases such as sexual transmitted diseases, anemia, malnutrition and bleeding, poverty, street children, emotional instability, complication during delivery, school attendance, academic performance, emotional behavior, broken marriages and miscarriages, increased family burden and abortion. This finding enables parents together with Tanzania government to work on factors that influencing early school pregnancy among secondary school students and Teachers should co-operate with parents to explore girls' potential and guide girls in the right way. This will help to reduce the burden of dropout of school girls from school caused by early school pregnancy among secondary school students.

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